

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Denis**FIRST NAME:** Peter**PROGRAM CODE:** DILT**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied xUS UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author Xdid did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-9)
3. The many forms of English (EUCLID 2019, 27-34)
4. Latin uses (EUCLID 2019, 56-61)
5. Punctuation (EUCLID 2019, 17-22)
6. Platforms (Zotero, Zotero connector)
7. Styles (EUCLID 2019, 44-55)

GETTING STARTED

1) **INTRODUCTION**

The first period of the first course of the doctoral program at Euclid University (EUCLID) seeks to establish a foundation upon which students integrate academic writing, and intellectual rigor can be applied throughout the program. Using an internationally accepted series of rules and prescriptions (Turabian 2018), the period helps those like me migrate to what will become familiar territory over the next several years.

In the few pages which follow, I will be applying the template and drawing from the course pack provided to explore some of the matters raised in this period. I have chosen themes that interest me and have elicited more attention, primarily because they are new in my experience.

I began my legal studies at the Université de Montréal in 1979. My studies at this vital Jesuit institution were entirely in French. The late 1970s was an era well before personal computers and the internet. Legal research was conducted with treatises and case books as well as summaries. I became a member of the Bar of Quebec in November of 1983, and my early practice was conducted almost exclusively in that language.

Several years later, my professional practice expanded to include legal matters outside of Quebec and required me to take the courses necessary to prepare me for that

practice. Those courses were delivered in English, Canadian English. The language differences represented a sea change in how I practiced law. I had to learn the law vocabulary in another language and express those terms before the English Canadian courts.

In the early 2000s, my path brought me to the United States and an appointment to the Faculty of Law at the University of Washington. I learned US law and US English. Later, I was able to undertake a master's program in Cyber Law at the Thomas Jefferson School of Law. This program introduced me to the Bluebook and, more particularly, to online legal research. The program brought me immense satisfaction, and the intervening years have convinced me that furthering my education in areas that I am passionate about is a worthy pursuit.

As may be predicted from this introduction, my conclusion will reinforce the pleasure I have derived from this first plunge into the EUCLID doctoral program.

2) WHITHER ENGLISH

I am pleased with the course pack and supporting material for this first period. While I have spoken English for my entire life, I have only, in the latter part, focused on English at an academic level. While teaching my students in Law School and Public Policy, I have found that I have added to adapt my understanding and application of the language to an American audience. This learning has been a mostly anecdotal experience with a few embarrassing moments of mangling the language's general economy. For this reason, I will be addressing some of the structural points gleaned from the course pack that I find particularly illuminating.

a) American English vs. the World

While the coursepack in chapter six is entitled American vs. British English (EUCLID 2019, 27), I feel a broader application at play. Growing up in Canada and watching Canadian (French and English), British, French, and American television was an exciting exercise to distinguish some of the respective languages' characteristics. When I attended English school, issues around spellings were often highlighted. Of note were words that British English used "our" while the same term in the American variation applied "or" instead (e.g., colour vs. color, favour vs. favor). In Canada, British spellings are applied in all our writing. The same was not correct concerning the words themselves. In most instances, usage dictated that American terms were used. For example, the word "boot" does not mean "trunk" in Canada. Instead, a boot is worn to trudge in the endless snow, while a trunk is decidedly the area in a car where you put your shovel to move the snow. The same principle applies to many of the areas identified in the course pack (EUCLID 2019, 28,29). One of the more curious challenges in the contrast of English between Canada, Britain, and America are the words "cheque/check." Canada uses the British spelling for the banking instrument, while the American formulation is applied very strongly to Canada's national sport, hockey. I am pleased that for my work at Euclid, I will

be employing only the American style of English and thereby disciplining myself to that style.

b) Punctuation

One of the more formidable writing challenges is to apply accepted rules of punctuation (EUCLID 2019 17, 22) and to do so consistently. With the advent of word processing and the multitude of advancements the intervening decades have provided, it is much easier to achieve a level of consistency in spelling, grammar, and punctuation than there existed when I first attended law school in 1979. My computer is set to American English and Canadian French, thereby allowing certain interchangeability in my writing, whether for work or to correspond with my family. Given the diverse backgrounds of my upbringing and education, I must always remind myself about punctuation matters. For example, the possessive in French is quite different from English. The coursepack EUCLID (2019, 18) provides a useful reminder of the English rules applied to the possessive. What I find helpful in the narrative is the distinction between the possessive singular and the plural. I know that I will be returning to this section as a reminder for future writing.

Similarly, the warning of applying punctuation within the quotation marks is useful as I have often seen the contrary. This reminder regarding the proper use of ellipses (EUCLID 2019, 49) is a helpful tool. I have discovered an ever-greater tendency to use ellipses in multiple forms of communication to the point that one wonders what has been omitted and whether something material has been edited out.

3) THE TRAGEDY OF PLAGIARISM

I have had the good fortune of being an instructor of record at Simon Fraser University in Vancouver, British Columbia, and the University of Washington (UW) in Seattle, Washington. One of the first warnings to students in all the classes I have taught is that plagiarism will not be tolerated. Despite that clear, clarion call, plagiarism remains rife, persistent, and pernicious. The UW is an agency of the State of Washington and is formed by statute (WAC, n.d.). The preceding law allows the UW to take action on student misconduct, prominent of which is the tragedy of plagiarism (WAC, n.d., 121). I use that expression deliberately as I have seen, firsthand, the implications of plagiarism and the necessity of a robust response to it in its' many forms.

Like all those with faculty appointments at the UW, I employ a series of software filters to assess whether or not a paper was plagiarized and, if so, to what extent. This tool and others like it are compelling and accurate in their assessments. When I was preparing my papers for my master's program at the Thomas Jefferson School of Law, I knew that my papers would be thusly scrutinized. Despite trusting that I had faithfully discharged my duties in eschewing plagiarism, I was always relieved when the filter returned negative. For this reason, I have long been mystified by students who persist in attempting to get away with this. In one case, I received a significant paper from a student at the master's

level that was 95 percent plagiarized. This result was so stunning that I ran the paper through two other filters and the conclusions were materially the same. Considering the statutory and policy obligations incumbent on instructors, the punishment for this breach of student conduct was severe.

When I first perused the course pack (EUCLID 2019, 5-12), I was delighted to see Euclid's prominence on calling out plagiarism. The university clarifies its policy and then provides a series of tools to allow for proper citations. In the section referenced above, I was pleased to read a definition and useful examples around paraphrasing. This section's critical element is that paraphrasing is a valuable tool in academic writing and, while helpful, must also be cited appropriately. As an instructor, I have often found students happy to paraphrase and then to pass off this work as original. I am glad that Euclid shares the same sense over this practice.

4) ZOTERO-POWERFUL AND TRICKY

I had had the immense good fortune to come of age at a time when personal computing was primarily the province of science fiction. Over the years, science fiction has become science fact, and I have been consistently delighted by the progress made. We manually performed legal citations during my years at the Universite de Montreal law school. Whole courses were devoted to doing this correctly for legal briefs and academic writing. Law students were employed for the sole purpose of reviewing every single citation in a brief or scholarly paper. When I switched over to English Canadian law, a whole new citation regimen was required. I would have been delighted to employ a software tool that could perform the tasks that ZOTERO seems to be able to perform so nimbly.

I am impressed by the facility that ZOTERO has in switching its form of citation and then cascading that information into the bibliographic record. These ZOTERO applications are well-adapted to what I observe as the Euclid paper format. The response paper and the major paper are two different academic vehicles, and I am pleased that Euclid has determined that both are elements of its pedagogical process. That ZOTERO is seamless in moving to and from these respective areas is something I look forward to observing firsthand.

At the time of this writing, I have watched the VIMEO recording attached to this first period at least ten times. I will attest that my learning curve is slow concerning the nuances of ZOTERO. I am still struggling with how best to cite the course pack. A variety of configurations have emerged (Cleenewerck, n.d.) rather than preferred (EUCLID 2019), each with peculiarities that seem to run afoul of this platform's general economy. I am undaunted by this and will watch the VIMEO some more, and by the time my dissertation is complete, I will have mastered the mysteries of ZOTERO.

3) CONCLUSION

I am excited to be undertaking the doctoral program at Euclid University. While I work at one of the foremost universities globally, the program offerings there do not elicit the same passion and interest as I see emerging from my brief time with Euclid. The UW is impressive, and I am proud to work and teach there. Sadly, its' offerings are not adapted to someone like me who prefers independent work, needs to do the course work online, and appreciates the focus and autonomy that the Euclid program offers.

I have chosen the focus areas for this first exercise to represent areas of interest, experience, and growth opportunities. I have been a problem-solver for most of my career and not a technician. I have substantial legal knowledge borne of experience and study but do not see myself as particularly "lawyerly." I believe in actionable solutions to real problems and have been able to fashion a very satisfying career by precisely doing that. Consequently, I see law, business, and academia as best exemplified when knowledge is collected, distilled, and applied to real-world problems. I do not favor the pursuit of knowledge merely for its' own sake. It would be nice to have that much time. My purpose in undertaking this program is to acquire knowledge that will allow me to consider real-world policy alternatives that could be added to Canada's strategic views on how it should be situated in the decades ahead. This view is consistent with what I achieved in my master's program, where the problem I sought to understand and, in so doing, help shape the challenges faced by Viet Nam in the digital age. I derived significant pleasure in adding my voice to those who have sought to assist that country, and I look forward to doing the in this program.

I know that the offerings will challenge me, and I will have to stay focused on advancing in the program when so many other demands will be made upon me, but I am resolved to move forward. The challenges I have faced with adapting to ZOTERO will linger until they are mastered. Similarly, I will learn the Turabian style of citation and master that as well, just as I learned and ultimately became conversant with the Bluebook.

I find the study of language and communication fascinating and recognize that I will have to park assumptions at the door and always revert to first principles. This is an excellent opportunity to avoid intellectual laziness and reliance on "gut" feelings. Checking and re-checking make us better and more on top of issues.

Finally, I will be reminded of my own experiences in the classroom and writing papers regarding plagiarism. As I proceed, I will have to find my voice and look to others' work as acknowledged support for that voice's furtherance.

This is going to be fun.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.